

Prospects to increase cropping intensity and production in 5-month irrigation areas

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In the 5-month irrigation areas of Indonesia, rains begin in September and land preparation for upland crops usually begins in October. But farmers cannot prepare the land for lowland rice culture until enough rain has fallen to soften the soil or until irrigation water comes in December. When water needs are met, the farmers prepare the seedbeds and begin to transplant about 30 to 40 days later. Pelita I/1 is harvested from 135 to 140 days after seedbed preparation or from mid-April to May. In May the irrigation water stops and the dry season begins. During this period about 90% of the rice land lies fallow. That area might

Average grain yield and income for superimposed study in 5-month irrigation areas. Cropping systems research, Nambahdadi, Lampung, Indonesia, 1975-76.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)			Income ^a (US\$/ha)			Total gross income (US\$/ha)
	1st crop	2nd crop	3rd crop	1st crop	2nd crop	3rd crop	
PelitaCorn-Rice bean	4.9	0.7	0.1	707	66	35	808
IR28-IR29-Mung beans	4.0	2.4	1.1	517	352	533	1,462
IR28-Sorghum-ratoon	3.6	2.4	-	525	88	-	613
IR28-Soybean-Mung beans	4.0	0.8	1.1	514	220	552	1,346
IR28-Peanut-Mung beans	4.3	0.3	1.0	625	158	449	1,232
IR28-Corn-Mung beans	4.0	2.1	1.2	511	198	597	1,372

^aPrices of crops determined at the conversion rate of Rp415 = US\$1.

be made more productive if farmers would plant a short-duration rice early in the rainy season, as soon as the irrigation water arrives or earlier. If IR28 were planted in November, it could be harvested 100 to 115 days later, in March or early April. After the harvest, there would still be enough water from rainfall and residual soil moisture to grow crops for 1 or 2 months. This concept was tested with six cropping patterns.

Two crops of early maturing rice

grown in the 5-month irrigation areas gave higher yields and gross returns than a single crop of the medium-maturing Pelita I/1 (see table).

A third crop of mung beans planted early in the rainy season, before the irrigation water arrives, can be productive and profitable. However, mung can be more logically considered as the first crop in the yearly sequence, as farmers consider it now in areas where upland crops are grown.

C171-136 upland rice compared with Dagge in a rice-corn cropping system in the Philippines

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For years, cropping systems researchers have attempted to find an upland rice variety better than the present one, Dagge, in an upland-rice site in Cale, Batangas province, Philippines. Until 1976 all varieties tested in farmers' fields failed, often because they could not withstand farmers' weeding practices, which involve passing a spike-toothed harrow, or *kalmot*, diagonally across the rows at from 10 to 20 days after emergence, followed by one or two interrow cultivations with a *lithao* (wooden furrow) and repeated hand weeding. The *kalmot* usually uprooted improved upland varieties. Furthermore, their shorter plant type often intensified weed problems later in the growing season, increasing labor requirements.

Dagge is harvested by removing individual panicles or cutting the entire

Weekly labor utilization and imputed weekly wage rates on 36 farms in Cale, Batangas province, Philippines, 1915-76.

Performance of C171-136 and Dagge as sole crop and intercrop with corn at constant and variable labor prices for weeding and harvesting, Cale, Batangas province, Philippines, 1977.

	Dagge alone ^a	C171-136 alone ^a	Dagge +corn ^b	C171-136 + corn ^b
<i>Rice</i>				
Yield (t/ha)	2.76	4.30	3.26	4.57
Tillers (no./sq m)	185	244	182	193
Gross returns ^c (US\$/ha)	525.03	818.50	620.54	869.66
<i>Corn</i>				
Yield (marketable ears)	—	—	12,466	13,400
Gross return ^d (US\$/ha)	—	—	144.22	154.97
Total return (US\$/ha)	525.03	818.50	764.76	1,024.63
Input costs ^e (US\$/ha)	77.55	77.55	157.82	157.82
<i>Labor requirement (man-h/ha)</i>				
Land preparation and seeding ^f	95	95	95	95
Weeding	163	95	90	234
Cultural practices ^f	35	35	54	64
Harvest	636	174	825	299 ^g
Total labor	929	399	1,064	692
<i>Assuming constant wages for weeding and harvest (\$0.17/h)^h</i>				
Labor costs (US\$/ha)	179.73	89.39	203.13	140.82
Total cost (US\$/ha)	257.28	166.94	361.09	298.78
Net return (US\$/ha)	267.76	651.56	403.67	693.76
Return to cash (US\$/ha)	0.60	1.28	0.48	0.75
<i>Weeding labor at \$0.07/h, harvest labor at \$0.34/h^h</i>				
Labor cost (US\$/ha)	271.70	109.93	337.41	171.70
Total costs (US\$/ha)	349.25	187.48	495.24	359.52
Net return (US\$/ha)	175.78	631.02	269.52	694.97
Return to cash (US\$/ha)	0.44	1.24	0.37	0.73
Return to labor (US\$/h)	0.48	1.86	0.57	1.25

^aAverage of 6 plots. ^bAverage of 3 plots. ^cPalay at US\$0.10/kg. ^dGreen ears of corn at US\$0.01/ear.

^eSeed and fertilizer: seed at US\$0.19/kg; fertilizer (ammonium sulfate) at US\$8.23/50 kg bag.

^fIncludes thinning, replanting, fertilizer application, and cultivation. ^gOne plot only for corn.

^hCultivation and land preparation at US\$0.34/h.

plant. Because it matures unevenly, the fields are harvested two or three times. Labor utilization peaks at weeding and harvesting (see figure), causing a substantial difference in imputed wages for hired labor through the year — an important factor in the evaluation of alternative technology.

In 1976 variety trials, the lines C171-136 (from the cross Sigadis/BPI-76) and C166-135 (Intan/B5580-A₁-15) outyielded Dagge. C171-136 was compared with Dagge in split fields under farmer management in Batangas in 1977.

As sole crop, C171-136 yielded an

average of 1.5 t/ha more than Dagge; as an intercrop with glutinous corn (which was harvested green), C171-136 yielded 1.3 t/ha more (see table). C171-136 and Dagge did not differ significantly in their effect on corn yields, but both yielded slightly higher as intercrops, probably because of the high nitrogen rate applied to the corn.

Because C171-136 matures evenly, the entire crop can immediately be harvested by sickle. Its low labor requirement for harvesting, combined with the increased gross returns, gave it an average increase in net returns of 143%

as sole crop and 80% as intercrop over Dagge. The computation assumed a cost of \$0.34/hour for any activity requiring animals and a constant cost of \$0.17/hour for all other labor inputs.

But it was considered more appropriate to value labor for hand weeding at \$0.07/hour and that for harvesting at \$0.34/hour, based on the imputed labor wage in Cale (see figure). At these wage rates, the average increase in net return of C171-136 over Dagge was 290% as sole crop and 158% as intercrop (see table).

C171-136 gave higher average returns to labor and cash. But the introduction of corn into the rice crop reduced returns to cash for both C171-136 and C166, and reduced returns to labor for C171-136. The rate at which nitrogen was applied to the corn (90 kg N/ha), in addition to the 75 kg N/ha applied to the rice, may have been too high.

The reduced labor for harvest of C171-136 also may reduce the turnaround time between rice and corn. That allows earlier planting, which results in significantly higher corn yields. C171-136 also produced more tillers per square meter (see table). Although its early growth is slightly slower than that of Dagge, its higher tiller number reduced weed competition.

Invitation to authors

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